

1 **Farmers' perceptions towards various risk sources:**
2 **Evidence from Tunisia**

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5 Zouhair Rached¹, Ali Chebil², Chokri Thabet³, Faten Khamassi⁴, Rania Sola³, Simone Piras⁵
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7 ¹ University of Carthage, National Institute of Agronomic Research of Tunis (INRAT), Tunis,
8 Tunisia.

9 ² University of Carthage, National Research Institute for Rural Engineering, Water and Forestry
10 (INRGREF), Tunis, Tunisia.

11 ³University of Sousse, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Meriem (ISACM), Sousse, Tunisia.

12 ⁴ University of Carthage, National Agronomic Institute of Tunisia (INAT), Tunis, Tunisia.

13 ⁵ The James Hutton Institute Craigiebuckler, Aberdeen AB15 8QH, Scotland, United Kingdom.
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15 Corresponding author: rached_zouhair@yahoo.fr
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38 **Abstract**

39 The objective of this paper is twofold. First, we analyze farmers' perceptions of various risk
40 sources. Second, we identify socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers that affect their
41 risk perceptions. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to a
42 sample of 931 farmers distributed between different regions of Tunisia (Central and North-
43 western). The data were analyzed using principal component analysis, cluster analysis, and a
44 bivariate probit model. We identify two components out of nine risk sources: socio-economic
45 and natural risks. The estimation results of the bivariate probit model reveal that rainfed farm-
46 ing, agriculture as main activity, young age, not being assisted from extension services, and
47 being a female farmer are significantly and positively related to higher perceived risk levels.
48 Location is only significant for the socio-economic component risk. We therefore suggest that
49 there is a need of targeted risk management strategies for different categories of farmers in
50 order to reduce risk and enhance the efficiency of agriculture in Tunisia.

51 **Keywords:** Farmers' perceptions; risk; principal component analysis; bivariate probit model;
52 Tunisia.

53 **Introduction**

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55
56 The agricultural sector in Tunisia is facing various sources of risks, such as climate stress,
57 diseases, financial, and market. These risks affect the performance of the sector (Jedder,
58 2018). The analysis of risk sources in agriculture and the perceived behavior of farmers to-
59 wards risks are thus of great importance. They allow for optimal management of the individu-
60 al farm and, at the macro-level, the agricultural sector. Indeed, understanding and assessing
61 risks enable farmers to make more informed decisions regarding the management of their
62 crops and livestock. This may include selecting more appropriate crops, using specific agri-
63 cultural practices, and managing better production factors such as water and fertilizers.

64 Furthermore, proper risk management provides protection for agricultural incomes. Climatic
65 uncertainties, crop diseases, pests, and other factors can lead to crop losses and, consequently,
66 financial losses for farmers. Identifying potential risks allows the implementation of mitiga-
67 tion measures to safeguard agricultural incomes. Risk management systems represent a chal-
68 lenge for academics, researchers and development planners, who lack full knowledge on
69 farmers' attitudes towards risk mitigation (Akthar et al., 2018; Kuszminski et al., 2018).

70 Understanding and managing agricultural risks allow to ensuring a stable and sufficient food
71 production to meet the growing needs of the population.

72 Agriculture plays a crucial role in global food security and environmental sustainability. By
73 identifying and addressing environmental risks associated with agricultural practices, it is
74 possible to promote and implement more sustainable practices to preserve natural resources
75 and reduce adverse effects on the ecosystem.

76 The study of farmers' perceptions towards various sources of risks is useful for effectively
77 ranking these risks and adopting appropriate mitigation strategies. This would enable farmers
78 to better cope with agriculture risks in rural areas, ultimately contributing to improved in-
79 comes. However, to the best of our knowledge, no studies in Tunisia have specifically ad-
80 dressed farmers' perceptions towards various risk sources.. Numerous studies conducted in
81 other countries have investigated risks from various sources (for instance, Conradie and Pies-
82 se, 2016; Akhtar et al., 2018; Islam et al., 2021).. However, the only study conducted in Tu-
83 nisia that specifically addresses farmers' perceptions of agricultural risks is by Jedder et al.
84 (2018), which focuses solely on the issue of pesticides.

85 Most of these studies employ probit or logit models for empirical analysis, whereas will uti-
86 lize a bivariate probit model.

87 Most of these studies employ probit or logit models for the empirical analysis, whereas this
88 study will be use a bivariate probit model.

89 The objectives of this work are to investigate the major sources of agricultural risks perceived
90 by Tunisian farmers, and identify the socio-demographic characteristics of farmers that affect
91 these risk perceptions.

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93 **2. Literature review**

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95 Agricultural risk has greatly interested the scientific community because, globally, producers
96 are confronted with numerous risks, including those related to the natural environment, pesti-
97 cide residues. Agricultural risk has greatly interested the scientific community because, glob-
98 ally, producers are confronted with numerous risk, including those related to the natural envi-
99 ronment, particularly, pesticides residues (Gurbuz, 2024) market fluctuations(Aleksandrova
100 and al.,2022), socio-political and policy fluctuations, and the biophysical environment (Ali et
101 al., 2019). Farming risks are increasing largely due to climate change, crop diseases, variabil-

102 ity of market prices of agricultural product (Mccarl et al., 1987; Liu et Petteola, 2005; Khan et
103 al., 2022), natural catastrophes, imperfect input and output markets (World bank, 2015), ab-
104 sence of or poor financial facilities, and inadequate tactics to manage risk such as credit
105 and/or crop insurance (Parshad et al., 1987).

106 Farmers can make better decisions related to crop management and technologies, including
107 assuming adaptive measures, if they have a good understanding of the risk sources (Halkos
108 and Skouloudis, 2020; Kunyanga, et al.2023). Furthermore, they must invest time and money
109 for developing appropriate measures to avoid or mitigate risks (Kresovic et al., 2018). Such
110 investments have great return potentials but, at the same time, high likelihood of failure (Akh-
111 tar et al., 2018). Noteworthy, farming itself is the major revenue source by which farm house-
112 holds identify and overcome the associated risks (Halkos et al.,2018).

113 In conclusion, agricultural risk is a complex issue, and farmers are confronted with various
114 types of risk. Therefore, the society, and particularly agricultural policy makers, should de-
115 velop a good understanding of farmers' risk perceptions. This knowledge is essential for ef-
116 fectively analyzing farmers' decisions (Adnan et al., 2018).

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118 **3. Materials and Methods**

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120 **3.1 Study area and data collection**

121 The data used in this study were collected through a survey in two regions (Fernana in
122 the North and Chebika in the Center of Tunisia). A stratified sampling method based on farm
123 size (small and large) was adopted. The survey was conducted in the framework of the inter-
124 national project H2020 FoodLAND ("Food and Local, Agricultural and Nutritional Diversi-
125 ty"), by project team members in collaboration with extension agents during the period
126 March-October 2021. The sample includes 413 farmers from Chebika and 500 farmers from
127 Fernana. The total farms in the Chebika and Fernana regions are about 5000 and 2000, respec-
128 tively. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect data about farm characteristics, utili-
129 zation of resources and technology, farm production systems, farmers' risk perception, and
130 socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers.

131 Figure 1 depicts the location of the study regions. Chebika, located in the governorate
132 of Kairouan, is characterized by a semi-arid climate with an average annual rainfall of around
133 290 mm. The primary crops grown in Chebika include wheat, vegetables (especially tomatoes
134 and chili peppers), and olive trees, which are mainly cultivated under irrigation. In contrast,

135 Fernana is located in a sub-humid climate area with an average annual rainfall of 700 mm.
136 Cereal crops are the major crops cultivated in Fernana, mainly cultivated under rainfall.
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Figure 1. Geographical locations of study areas

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3.2. Analytical approach

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144 Our methodological approach consists of two subsequent steps. The first one uses
145 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for reducing the dimensionality of our data, increasing
146 interpretability while minimizing information loss, with the aim of condensing the sources of
147 risk from nine to fewer categories. The second step involves econometric modeling using a
148 bivariate probit model to identify the impact of socio-economic characteristics of producers
149 on these fewer categories of risks.

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3.2.1. Principal Component Analysis

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153 Principal component analysis (PCA) is a valuable technique for handling large data
154 sets, particularly when dealing with high-dimensional data that can be difficult to interpret. Its
155 main goal is to reduce the dimensionality of the data while retaining as much variance as possible. By transforming the original variables into a new set of uncorrelated variables (principal

156 components), PCA allows for a more concise representation of the data (Jolliffe and Cadima,
 157 2016; Wiley, 1981).

158 In this study, PCA will be employed to establish a simplified typology of risk sources,
 159 based on the perception of the farmers interviewed. Initially, nine risk sources were defined
 160 and scored in the questionnaire using Likert scales (1 = low perceived risk, 5 = high perceived
 161 risk). These are illustrated in Table 1.

162 Table 1: Types of risk defined and used in this study analysis

Risk sources	Variable explanation	Modalities
worry_dispos	Worry: Extent to which "dispossession of land" is a worry for the future for the farmer	1 = Not at all important, 2 = Slightly important, 3 = Somewhat important, 4 = Moderately important, 5 = Extremely important
worry_lossfarm	Worry: Extent to which "loss of off-farm job" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_prcfeed	Worry: Extent to which "cost increase (price of fertiliser or seed)" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_income	Worry: Extent to which "income reduction" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_health	Worry: Extent to which "health (disease)" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_disease	Worry: Extent to which "infestation/pest" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_drought	Worry: Extent to which "drought" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_starv	Worry: Extent to which "food shortage/starvation" is a worry for the future for the farmer	
worry_flood	Worry: Extent to which "flooding" is a worry for the future for the farmer	

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164 3.2.2. Bivariate probit model

165 After calculating farmers' perceptions of the two types of risk using PCA, a bivariate probit
 166 model is used to identify the factors influencing farmers' perception of these types of risk.
 167 This model type accounts for possible correlation between the two binary dependent variables
 168 (Greene, 2003). The joint regression modeling framework for the analysis is defined as fol-
 169 lows.

170 Let us assume that there are two dependent variables in the bivariate model (Y_{i1} , Y_{i2}), for $i =$
 171 $1, \dots, n$, where n represents the sample size. The observed dependent variables (Y_{i1} , Y_{i2})
 172 relate to corresponding latent variable and which are unobserved.

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175 Where η_{1i} and η_{2i} are the unobservable latent variables, X_{1i} et X_{2i} are vectors of independent
176 variables, β_1 et β_2 represent vectors of model parameters, and ϵ_{1i} et ϵ_{2i} are the residuals
177 associated with the model. The residuals are normal with means zero, variances one, and cor-
178 relation ρ . If ρ is significantly different from 0, then the two random components of the model
179 are correlated.

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183 The probability of event ($Y_{i1} = 1, Y_{i2} = 1$) can be defined as

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185 Where Φ_2 is the bivariate normal cumulative distribution function. Greene (2003) provides
186 maximum likelihood estimation of the parameters in the bivariate probit model.

187 The identification of factors expected to be associated with farmers' perceptions towards var-
188 ious risk sources is based on the literature (Adnan et al., 2018; Jedder et al.2018; Ali et al.,
189 2019, Islam et al., 2021). The resulting independent variables used in the empirical analysis
190 are listed in Table 2. These are farm size, farming practices (irrigated or rainfed), professional
191 situation, age, level of education and gender of the farm manager, location, land tenure, and
192 receiving assistance from extension services. The two binary dependent variables are the per-
193 ceived risk levels for the two major components identified from PCA. Both the PCA and the
194 bivariate probit model were estimated using the SPSS program 20.1.

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196 **4. Results and discussions**

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198 **4.1. Principal component analysis**

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200 Before implementing PCA, preliminary tests must be implemented to assess the ade-
201 quacy of the dataset to applying this data reduction method, namely the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
202 (KMO) and Bartlett tests. The results of these tests are reported in Table 3. As we can see,
203 both tests confirm this adequacy of PCA, confirming the goodness of dimensions reduction
204 from the considered variables. In fact, KMO test indicates a high value (0.858), and Bartlett's

205 test of sphericity is statistically significant at the 1% level. These results suggest that the da-
 206 taset is appropriate for implementing PCA.

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Table 3: Results of KMO and Bartlett tests

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sampling Adequacy Measure		0.858
	chi-square approximation	4,231.27
Bartlett's test of sphericity	ddl	28
	Significance of Bartlett	0.000

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209 The total variation explained by all the principal component, the Eigenvalues, the Variability
 210 values (%) and the Cumulative values (%) are reported in Table 4. Eight principal compo-
 211 nents explain 100% of the total variation. If the eigenvalues are above 1, it indicates that the
 212 evaluated principal component weight values are reliable (Mohammadi and Prasanna, 2003).
 213 Equally, Iezzoni and Pritts (1991) report that if the eigenvalues are greater than 1 (PCs with
 214 eigenvalue >1.0), the PC is more informative than the original variables. Eigenvalues were
 215 4.3 for PC1 (the first component) and 1.1 for PC2 (the second component). As a result, two
 216 principal component axes were retained. The first principal component explains 54.3% of the
 217 total variation (PC1). The second one (PC2) explains 14.1% of the total variation. The cumu-
 218 lative ratio of these two primary components in the total variation is 68.4%.

Table 4: Results of the principal component analysis

Compound (PC)	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squares of Retained Factors			Sum of Squares of Retained Factors for Rotation		
	Total	% of variance	% cumu- lated	Total	% of variance	% cumu- lated	Total	% of variance	% cumu- lated
1	4;343	54;283	54;283	4;343	54;283	54;283	3;416	42;695	42;695
2	1;128	14;101	68;384	1;128	14;101	68;384	2;055	25;689	68;384
3	0;865	10;807	79;190						
4	0;507	6;332	85;522						
5	0;442	5;520	91;042						
6	0;354	4;425	95;466						
7	0;225	2;812	98;278						
8	0;138	1;722	100;000						

219 According to Table 5, the following variables have the highest loading on first principal com-
 220 ponent (PC1), with their corresponding coefficients: worry_dispos (0.913), worry_loss_farm
 221 (0.863), worry_prc_feed (0.807), worry_income (0.699), worry_health (0.652), and wor-

222 ry_disease (0.606). In the second principal component, the variables worry_drought (0.684),
 223 worry_starvation (0.683), and worry_flood (0.468) have the highest loadings on this compo-
 224 nent, respectively. Based on these variables and loadings, we can label component 1 as repre-
 225 senting “socio-economic risks” and component 2 as representing “natural risks”.

226 Table 5: Compound Matrix after rotation

Sources risk	Compound	
	Socio-Economic risks (1)	Natural risks (2)
worry_dispos	0;913	0;020
worry_lossfarm	0;863	-0;107
worry_prceed	0;807	0;445
worry_income	0;699	0;461
worry_health	0;652	0;537
worry_disease	0;606	0;483
worry_drought	0;165	0;684
worry_starv	-0;066	0;683
worry_flood	0;163	0;468
Extraction Method: Principal compound analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with normalization of Kaiser.		
a. The rotation converged after 3 iterations.		

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228 4.2 Descriptive analysis of variables used in the bivariate model

229 In the first step of this study, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to
 230 establish a simplified typology of risk sources based on the perception of the farmers inter-
 231 viewed. Initially, nine risk sources were defined and scored using Likert scales. The two prin-
 232 cipal components identified from the PCA analysis are used to obtain dependent variables for
 233 the bivariate probit model. The two dependent variables, which we name “econo” for soci-
 234 economic risks (Y1) and “natural” for natural risks (Y2) take value 1 if the average perceived
 235 level of the factors (Likert score) is higher than 2.5, and 0 otherwise. More precisely, for each
 236 risk factor, we average the Likert scores of the statements that associate with the respective
 237 PC.

238 Descriptive statistics for the variables used in bivariate probit mode are reported in Table 6

239 % Y1 and % Y2 (dependent variables).

240 Table 6 indicates that a significant portion of farmers (40%) have an area of land
 241 smaller than 2 hectares. The second largest group (34% of the total farms) have between 2 and
 242 5 hectares. Only 26% of total farms have an area larger than 5 hectares. Concerning the de-
 243 mographic profile of farmers, 55% of them are aged between 40-62 years. Also, the majority
 244 (67%) of the farmers have completed primary or secondary education levels. The sample in-
 245 cludes 70% of men and 30% of women. With respect to agricultural practices, 43% (less than
 246 half) of the farms are irrigated, indicating a reliance on natural water sources for agricultural
 247 activities.

248 Table 6 : Dependent and independent variables used in binary model

	Observed variables	Options	%	Min	Max	Average
Demographic characteristics	Variable Dependent type of risk (VI): Natural Socio-economic	VI=1 if score's type >2.5 ; VI=0 if scores <2.5				
	Education level (1=higher than primary, 0=illiterate and primary)	0	25%			
		1	75%			
	Age (Farmer's age, larger than 18 years)	[0-40]	31%	18		
		[40-62*]	55%			
		over 62	14%			
Gender (Farmer's gender)	Male=1	70%				
	Female=0	30%				
Farm characteristics	Location	1 = Chebika,	46%			
		0 = Fernana	54%			
	Farm Size (Total size of the land used by the farmer, regardless of the tenure status, in hectares)	Low 2 ha	40%	1	127	3
		[2-5ha]	34%			
		[5-10ha]	20%			
		Over than 10ha	6%			
	Irrigation mode (Irrigation of any crops by the farmer in the last agricultur- al/production year)	Irrigated=1	43%			
		no irrigated=0	57%			
Land tenure	1 = own property	85%				
	0 = otherwise	15%				
Institutionnel and communication factors	Assistance from extension services	1 = Yes,	33%			
		0 = No	66%			
	Professional situation of producers	1 = agriculture	69%			
		0 = no	31%			

249 *62 ans is the pension age in Tunisia

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251 4.3 Results of the bivariate probit model

252 The results of the bivariate probit model indicate that there is a correlation between the
 253 two types of risks, which is significant at 5% ($\rho=0.44\%$) (Table 7). The estimation results

254 reveal that relying on rainfed farming (i.e., having no irrigation), engaging in agriculture as
 255 main activity, young age, no assistance from extension services, and being a female farmer
 256 are all significantly and positively related to higher perceived risk levels for both components
 257 of risks (socio-economic, and natural). The results about irrigation, assistance from extension
 258 services, and engaging in agriculture as the main economic activity are all in line with our
 259 hypothesized sign of the effect, while other variables are either not significant or we did not
 260 have a defined hypothesis in terms of sign. Location is only statistically significant for the
 261 socio-economic component, with farmers from Chebika perceiving lower levels of risk in this
 262 sense. This can be explained with Fernena (the other sampling location) being in a poorer,
 263 more remote area of the country, with smaller farms on average. The major factors affect the
 264 perceived level of socio-economic and natural risks are irrigation, professional situation, age
 265 and extension services. These results suggest that in order to reduce risk (as well as its percep-
 266 tion) and enhance the efficiency of agriculture in Tunisia there is a need of targeted risk man-
 267 agement strategies for different categories of farmers.

268 Table 7: Effect of farmers' socio-characteristics on the perceived risk types

Characteristics	Types of risks				Marginal effects for
	Socio-Economic risks		Natural risks		Eco=1 and Nat=1
	Coefficient	t-Student	Coefficient	t-Student	Coefficient
Size	-0;001	-0;22	-0;003	-0;59	-0;001
Irrigation	-0;781***	-8;30	-0;588**	-6;30	-0;256***
Professionnel Situation	0;108***	3;18	0;148***	4;46	0;045***
Age	-0;008**	-1;98	-0;010***	-2;72	-0;003***
Education level	-0;017	-0;38	-0;025	-0;54	-0;007
Gender	-0;092	-0;86	-0;248***	-2;26	-0;057*
Location (Chebika)	-0;279***	-2;60	-0;077	-0;70	-0;071**
Tenure	0;094	0;75	0;047	0;37	0;027
Extention	-0;188*	-1;60	-0;264**	-2;38	-0;083**
Constant	0;574	1;63	0;816	2;32	
/Atrho	0;45	8;06			
Rho	0;45	0;05		0;340	
LR test of Rho=0 Chi2=69;934 Prob> chi2=0;000					

269 *** significant at 1%; ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%.

270 Conclusion and policy implications

271 This paper investigated farmers' perceptions towards various risk sources and identi-
 272 fied the main factors influencing these perceptions. We used principal component analysis
 273 and a bivariate probit model for the empirical analysis of data obtained from a sample of 931

274 farmers distributed between two different regions of Tunisia (Central and Northwestern). The
275 principal component analysis identified two components of farmers' risk perceptions from
276 nine sources of risk: socio-economic and natural. The estimation results of the bivariate probit
277 model reveal that rainfed farming, having agriculture as main the activity, young age, lack of
278 assistance from extension services, and being a female farmer are significantly and positively
279 associated with higher perceived risk levels for both socio-economic and natural risks. Being
280 located in Northwestern Tunisia is related to higher perceived socio-economic risks.

281 The study therefore suggests that there is a need of targeted risk management strate-
282 gies for different categories of farmers to mitigate risks and enhance the efficiency of agricul-
283 ture in Tunisia. Hence, it is essential to design risk mitigation strategies that are tailored to
284 each region and to specific to each type of risk, utilizing an appropriate measure. In the future,
285 this research could be extended by analyzing risk sources for different production systems to
286 identify specific risk management instruments suitable for each system.

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